

Guilford Budd: A Second Look

by Edmond Iniguez

Every now and then, a figure from the past emerges out of the depths of history with a story that seems too good to be true – a history writer’s dream... But things are not always as they seem. This perceived good fortune could be a product of incorrect record keeping or because of errors made by the historian or the inevitable corruptions that always infect historic facts as they percolate to a metaphoric surface. Or they are the result of deliberate lies or careful intrigues – tall tales - manufactured in the past that are easily passed on as fact if not carefully examined. Guilford Budd is one of these historic figures.

In the April 2022 issue of the [Pueblo Lore](#), the official mouthpiece of the Pueblo Historical Society, an article appeared entitled “Judge Guilford Courthouse Budd.” It will be remembered that in this article, mention was made that Guilford Budd was Pueblo’s first African American to make political bids for several public offices including the U.S. Congress; however, there is some confusion. The article includes a statement taken from his obituary which stated that Budd had been “demented ever since he ran for congress in 1874, which by the way proved a very serious joke so far as the old man was concerned.” There seems to be some kind of contradiction in play here... Did Budd run for public office as a willing aspirant to political acclaim or was this, indeed, some kind of joke? In other words, was the political campaign ‘real’ in the sense that Budd considered himself a viable candidate and he was campaigning for an equally viable electorate that accepted him as a considerable candidate – or was this something else? Could the political campaigns of Budd be tall tales?

Regardless of these assumed political aspirations, Budd’s life does deserve to be remembered – and should. But before making a fuller examination into the life of Guilford Budd, we need to clarify the tall tales built around Budd.

First, quick consideration must be made as to who Guilford Budd was to determine a basic answer if Budd would be a fully viable candidate in the eyes of voters at the time. Guilford was an African American man, a former slave, who had been in Pueblo before the Town of Pueblo was even incorporated and should be considered an original pioneer. For the time, he was somewhat prosperous, although not fabulously wealthy, and was known to be accommodating, kind and a man who was a hard worker. He was also known to be rather fun loving, who imbibed in drink a little too much and was prone to fits of excess, wild adventure and bad luck. It was also known that Budd was illiterate, could barely read and could not write – although he did seem to have skill with numbers. His illiteracy is confirmed in the records of his estate that followed his death.¹ Contained in these are the humble X marks he and his wife made when signing legal documents. These facts are also revealed in the details of the “massive one-and-a-quarter page story,” published in the Colorado Daily Chieftain on June 1, 1890, that was mentioned in the April 2022 Lore article. Beyond the obvious racial considerations which should be kept in mind, could Budd’s illiteracy, most importantly, allow him to be accepted as a viable candidate for any public office?

Coincidentally, Budd himself never expressed his desire to run for any kind of political office and, in fact, he always stated that he had no political aspirations – but would serve if elected. These words, unfortunately, helped to contribute to the myths built around him. Upon closer inspection, it becomes clear that the political campaigns he experienced were all seemingly forced upon him as someone else made him a candidate – but these will be examined shortly.

Before the events reported in the April 2022 article (that centered around 1874), a curious event was reported in 1869, which is also the earliest public mention of Guilford Budd in Pueblo. This event can be seen as a kind of foreshadow to the impetus behind Budd’s so-called political ventures and the

¹ State of Colorado. “Budd, Guilford C.” Probate Record. State of Colorado Archives. State of Colorado. Denver. 1887.

events of 1874 - the fabled congressional run. According to the Colorado Weekly Chieftain of August 26, 1869, a rather serious drunken row began along the banks of the Arkansas. As the fight continued, one of the rowdies found his way to a nearby saloon and asked for a policeman. Apparently, an equally rowdy bunch at the saloon saw an opportunity for ill-conceived sport and one of their number introduced himself to the stranger as the Mayor of Pueblo, somehow produced a Warrant for Arrest and directed the river rowdy to the house of Guilford Budd. The river rowdy was told that Guilford was the local policeman and would put a stop to the fracas – but, of course, the saloon rowdy was not the mayor and Guilford was not a policeman, nor was he vested with any kind of municipal authority to affect an arrest. For some reason, Guilford did respond to the call – but luckily the fight was over by the time he got there.

Curiously, not two weeks later, Guilford was presented with a nomination to run for the office of Justice of the Peace by Pueblo locals. This nomination, mentioned in the April 2022 article, was reported by the Rocky Mountain News Daily in Denver on September 10, 1869 and this article directly mentions that Guilford's nomination was an act of spite because of the repetitive acts of Pueblo politicians who lost their bids for nomination with one party or another, then promptly switched parties and ran on the other ticket. John Stokes, the man Guilford stood against, had done just this after he lost the nomination for Justice of the Peace as a Republican and promptly changed to a Democrat and won the nomination there.

Similarly, the September 9, 1869 issue of the Colorado Daily Chieftain did not clearly report the aforementioned motive but did publish the bitter remarks made by the candidates in question regarding the 'betrayals' they endured at the hands of their former parties. Also, a letter from some of Pueblo's prominent citizens was printed on the same day that begs Guilford to stand as a nominee for Justice of the Peace. The gracious acceptance of Guilford Budd follows, who stated that his nomination was "flattering and complimentary," and added that "though [I] am no aspirant for political honors, I cannot

refuse the spontaneous call of my fellow citizens.” Although there were forty-five people who addressed the letter to Guilford Budd to run for office, he received only 12 votes.² From these events, it is easy to surmise that something very curious is going on in Pueblo at the time - and Guilford Budd seems to have been caught in the middle of something he has no control of.

In 1873, on March 21, 23 and 25, mention is made in the Colorado Daily Chieftain that Guilford was an unofficial candidate for mayor – and went so far on the 23rd to say “that alarm is increased by observing Budd bowing, lifting his hat even, and smiling benignly on all of our citizens” in an attempt “well calculated to deceive the very elect.” The short article then goes on to mention that the other candidate won’t even make the attempt to smile – but he will distribute cigars. With this, one gets the impression that another instance of ill-intended and less-than-magnanimous spite might be in effect.

Then, the following year, another letter was published in the Colorado Daily Chieftain on August 28, 1874 that set the events in motion for the mythical “first African American to run for office” as mentioned in the April 2022 article. This letter was purportedly from “John E. Caique and One Thousand More” that begged for Guilford Budd to stand as the no-less-than sixth independent candidate for Congress for the Territory of Colorado. And of course, Guilford blithely accepted the very same day. The events that followed his acceptance were all related in the earlier Lore account (complete with cartoons!) – and should be considered somewhat factual as reported, but the motive behind the nomination should already be questioned as being dubious as well as Budd’s being completely compliant.

Mercifully, after the dust settled following all the ridiculous events, the Chieftain came clean on September 16, 1874: “Judge Budd has at length come to the remarkably wise conclusion that he has been made a fool of.”

Regardless, once again, on March 30, 1876, there is an attempt at a repeat performance – and

² “Election Returns.” Colorado Weekly Chieftain. September 16, 1869. Pueblo, CO

the situation behind the 1874 events becomes clearer. The Colorado Daily Chieftain mentioned that “some of the fun loving boys [were] trying to persuade his Honor Judge Guilford Budd to be a candidate at the coming city election.” The Chieftain added that if he agrees, “some of the lively scenes...of a couple of years ago may be repeated.” In response, Guilford seems to have finally learned his lesson when, on March 31, 1877, the Colorado Daily Chieftain reported that Budd was “necessarily compelled to refuse [anyone] the privilege of voting for [him for] mayor” and he absolutely declined to serve if elected – although the next day he recanted this decision and did consent to serve if elected.

And there it is: public fun at the expense of Guilford Budd... It seems that these so-called political bids were nothing more than very serious practical jokes which no-one took seriously – except Guilford Budd.

After some eight years of this public humiliation, Budd’s name became known up and down the Front Range and newspapers across the region used the “campaigns” of Budd as metaphors for bad elections, poor political strategies and ridiculous candidates and mention was frequently made of the antics of 1874 as something that was comical, ridiculous and unbelievable. Unfortunately, Guilford had to bear the brunt of all of this, and as we get to know him as a simple man, the tragedy only becomes clearer. Strangely, these trends to defame and embarrass him continued after his death – but there is another motive behind this which we shall explore later...

And finally, regarding the title ‘Judge.’ I hope that the reader can deduce that there was no respect or love that came with the use of this title and it was one that he probably came to despise as time went on - which is why I will not refer to Guilford Budd by anything except his name. He was also called “His Honor,” “Honorable” and “Esquire” as well as “Colonel.” During the campaign of 1874, new epithets were introduced such as: “Southern Blonde” and “Unbleached Candidate...”³

At this point I must beg the reader to forgive me of the time I have taken to dispel the myths

³ Colorado Daily Chieftain, September 17, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

and fables connected with Guilford Budd. The article of April 2022 was nothing but a repetition of the public fables and myths that had been established over one hundred years before. We can only guess as to why these things happened, but it must be understood that Guilford Budd was not a candidate in our understating of the word, but was more of a victim. But behind all of the antics, misfortunes and alleged political ambitions, there was a real man that no one knows.

Nailing down the life of Guilford Budd has not been easy. He was born sometime in the 1820s. Assumptions have been made as to where he was born with the most obvious being because of his elaborate middle name, "Courthouse." When associated with his first name, this leads to the assumption that he was from North Carolina – but there is no real way to know, because no record of his early life was kept. The 1870 U.S. Federal Census, reported that he was from Arkansas while the 1880 census reported he was from Tennessee and another mention was made that he was from Virginia.⁴ Another document made at the end of his life recorded that he was born in Alabama.⁵ But the simple fact is that Guilford Budd was an African American man born into slavery.

It should be understood that Guilford's early life took place during a time when slavery was still a very accepted institution in the United States. Personal information was not kept regarding slaves and slaves were usually recorded under the name of the owner.

He first enters the historical record as an individual in 1863. The Provost General of The United States for the Department of the Missouri recorded that a man named Guilford Budd, approximately 40 years of age, with a large build and black skin was taken as a captive of war on March 21 and was "entitled to the protection of all officers of the United States." After this date, we hear nothing of him until the aforementioned events of 1869...

We do know that Guilford Budd did arrive in Pueblo with his wife Annie and a daughter Amanda

⁴ Stone, Wilbur F. "Early Pueblo and the Men Who Made It." Colorado Magazine. Vol. VI. No. 6. November 1929.

⁵ "Guilford Budd - Patient 455." January 4, 1887. Patient General Register. Colorado State Insane Asylum. Colorado Mental Health Institute Museum. Pueblo, CO.

in either 1866 or 1867. Mention of this was made in the July 4, 1876 address of Judge Wilbur Stone titled “Early Pueblo and the Men Who Made It.” In this address, delivered on a sweltering Independence Day in a grove of cottonwood trees on the banks of the Arkansas, Stone declared that Guilford Budd was, indeed, the first African American in Pueblo – although the exact words Stone used described Budd as “an old Virginia darkey” and that he was “the first ‘n-----r in Pueblo.”⁶ We should fairly expand this statement to say that Guilford Budd, his wife Annie and their daughter Amanda were the first African Americans and the first African American family in Pueblo. Additionally, the 1870 census does record them as a family unit and the only African American family unit in Pueblo (and three of only 15 African Americans in the Town of Pueblo by 1870).

Guilford, himself, expanded on his history in 1874 during the famous speech he made when running for congress. He said that he escaped slavery in 1860 and a reward of \$2,000 was put on his head. He adds that when he fled, he had to leave his wife behind and that he was very sorry “to part with that woman.”⁷

A little more of his pre-Pueblo past was revealed following his death. His obituary stated that he “came to Pueblo from Ft. Union, New Mexico in 1866 or 1867,” and while at Ft. Union he earned “considerable money which he had made laboring and acting as porter in a hotel.”⁸

Mention of this money is interesting, because the Pueblo County Inverted Index of Real Estate Transfers, Jan. 1867 to April 25, 1873 records that Budd had purchased several town lots in 1870 and that transfer of real estate was taking place to 1872 and after.⁹ We also know that he operated a barber shop, the first of its kind in Pueblo,¹⁰ and expanded his business by opening a formal barber shop in “the

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ “Judge Budd On The Stump.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. September 3, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

⁸ “Guilford Court House Budd.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. February 25, 1887. Pueblo, CO.

⁹ Pueblo County Inverted Index of Real Estate Transfers, Jan. 1867 to April 25, 1873. Sept. 2, 1870, Sept. 8, 1870 and Apr. 16, 1872. Pueblo County. Pueblo, CO

¹⁰ “Judge Budd Comes to Grief.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. Feb 16, 1875. Pueblo, CO.

old City Hotel.”¹¹

In the autumn of 1872, he began construction of a brick-fronted building on Santa Fe Avenue “opposite the Drovers”¹² and “just below the Star Restaurant.”¹³ The cost of the building was estimated as being \$1200¹⁴, or approximately \$28,000 today. Additionally, he owned property which he rented to others as residences.¹⁵ But Budd did not limit his livelihood to real estate...

Throughout the 1870s he performed irregular jobs for both the City and County of Pueblo that ranged from “scavenging” to grave digging to hauling to “cleaning out an out-house.”¹⁶ He also served as a local cowboy and tended to the town herds of cows and horses,¹⁷ painted houses and fences¹⁸ and, most interestingly, was the first sexton at the City Cemetery (now Pueblo Pioneer Cemetery) from its inception¹⁹ to sometime after June 1875.²⁰ He stated that he was responsible for burying “about three hundred people” and was sexton “going on four years” in 1874.²¹

Budd also expressed a kind of matter-of-fact business pragmatism that came with his wife’s venture as a restaurateur. As also mentioned in the April 2022 article, his wife Annie opened the Delmonico Restaurant in 1874, but Budd also proclaimed that any debts she might accrue were hers and hers alone because “she is doing business in her own name.”²² He also expressed concern regarding the building on Santa Fe Avenue in that the insurance costs were going to be high.²³

What is more, in 1875, he was caught running an unlicensed gambling and whisky den that was

¹¹ Colorado Daily Chieftain. June 2, 1872. Pueblo, CO.

¹² Colorado Daily Chieftain. October 19, 1872. Pueblo, CO.

¹³ Colorado Daily Chieftain, November 5, 1872. Pueblo, CO.

¹⁴ Colorado Daily Chieftain. December 30, 1872. Pueblo, CO.

¹⁵ Colorado Daily Chieftain. May 5, 1874 and May 29, 1879. Pueblo, CO.

¹⁶ No less than a dozen mentions of these ‘odd jobs’ were made in the Colorado Daily Chieftain from June 1875 to October 1877.

¹⁷ Colorado Daily Chieftain. May 17, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

¹⁸ Colorado Daily Chieftain. October 16, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

¹⁹ “Judge Budd on the Stump.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. September 3, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

²⁰ “County Commissioners.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. June 10, 1875. Pueblo, CO.

²¹ “Judge Budd on the Stump.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. September 3, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

²² Colorado Daily Chieftain. June 27, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

²³ Colorado Daily Chieftain. November 5, 1872. Pueblo, CO.

popular with the small African American community in Pueblo. In regards to this event, he paid \$44 in fines and costs but seems to have suffered some kind of schism with “those of his own race” as he vowed to never deal with them again. It was also mentioned that he was proud of his wealth and of his early residency in Pueblo – and that because of this, he was accused of “putting on airs” – which did not make him popular.²⁴ This same year, he began his final business venture which seems to be the one he stuck with – an expressman. First mention of this was on Sept 4, 1875²⁵ and was recorded as his profession when he was admitted to the State Insane Asylum just before his death.²⁶

Guilford Budd, probably due to the unfortunate fame he garnered during the 1870s, was a frequent local celebrity whose instances of tomfoolery and scrapes with the law were published frequently throughout the 1870s and into the 1880s just before his death – and these only accentuated his fantastic preponderance for bad luck and ‘wild’ antics. Of course, we must assume that some kind of cloud had already been placed above his head for one reason or another by the public at large – and the frequent published mentions of him in these less than complimentary reflections only reinforce this. In the interest of respect for the dead, direct mention of these instances will not be repeated here.

He and his wife frequently used the version of their surname we are most familiar with: Budd. They also used the name Budds interchangeably. Also, during the 1874 congressional speech, Guilford mentioned that he was “a native of the Cherokee nation.”²⁷ Whether true or not, he was made to pay for having made this statement as mention was made that he was seen “running wild on the coast of Africa some thirty years before,” but this story had to be a rumor since he claimed to be a mix of Cherokee and Spanish descent.²⁸

²⁴ “Judge Budd Comes to Grief.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. February 16, 1875. Pueblo, CO.

²⁵ Colorado Daily Chieftain. September 4, 1875. Pueblo, CO.

²⁶ “Guilford Budd - Patient 455.” January 4, 1887. Patient General Register. Colorado State Insane Asylum. Colorado Mental Health Institute Museum. Pueblo, CO.

²⁷ “Judge Budd on the Stump.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. September 3, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

²⁸ Colorado Daily Chieftain. August 30, 1874. Pueblo, CO.

Beyond all of this, an event occurred that predated the political messes, save the initial 1869 Justice of the Peace foolishness. In 1871, an editorial was published in the Colorado Weekly Chieftain on July 27. The editorial questioned the state of Pueblo society and the increased lawlessness that seemed to be overtaking the territory. The editorial goes on to say that the citizens of pueblo were fairly disgusted at a recent occurrence that could resurrect very early Pueblo's habit of frequent vigilante justice and public hangings. The editorial takes focus with the sentence, "Here in our midst has dwelt for several years an inoffensive negro (sic.) called Guilford Budd."²⁹

The report of the incident,³⁰ published the same day, was simply horrifying... Apparently, two men, Tom Green and John Schwer, operated a saloon in Pueblo – and Green, "for some reason...had a grudge against...Budd." In fact, Green had, on occasion, "driven [Budd] out of the saloon" by throwing glasses at his head.

Budd happened to enter the saloon on the day in question to deliver ice, and present was a man named Hugh Cameron, described as a "reprobate [and] worthless character" who was "indebted to Budd for a small sum under two dollars." Budd, seeing Cameron, asked for the money to be returned to him and was violently refused. As Budd dejectedly headed for the door, Cameron leapt upon him and drove Budd to the floor while Green closed and locked the saloon doors. Thereupon, Cameron began to beat and scratch at Budd's face and proceeded to bite down upon Budd's upper lip. Cameron, who chewed at Budd's face, succeeded in biting off half of Budd's lip, "from the nostril to the corner of his mouth" and then proceeded to severely beat him and "pounded him upon his head with all his force, at the same time using the most foul and disgusting epithets." Apparently, a window was open, and passersby outside the saloon crowded around it in response to the noise, and as some tried to enter the saloon, including the co-operator John Schwer, Green was seen to prevent them from entering. Soon,

²⁹ "Whither Are We Drifting?" Colorado Weekly Chieftain. July 27, 1871. Pueblo, CO.

³⁰ "Fiendish Atrocity." Colorado Weekly Chieftain. July 27, 1871. Pueblo, CO.

the crowd began to threaten to break down the doors – which they did – and this prompted Cameron to escape out the back.

Budd, who was crying and groaning, was helped to his feet. He was “giddy, faint and reeling,” had “blood spurting from his mouth, his lip chewed out, his face cut, swollen and mangled until he was scarcely recognizable” and was, “with great difficulty...kept on his feet while he reeled to the door.” His wounds were tended by Dr. Pembroke Thombs, who quite ironically would be the superintendent of the State Insane Asylum when Budd was committed in 1887.

Eventually, Green and Cameron were arrested and thrown into jail, whereupon the two attempted to escape several times - and Green eventually did - but the damage had been done. The people of Pueblo were disgusted. Mention was made that Green had “too much regard for his personal safety” to dare attempt to return to Pueblo,³¹ that the “blood of the people” of Pueblo was “thoroughly roused” and they threatened any would-be criminals to find “some other place where they will have a better chance of keeping whole necks than they will find here.”³²

Additionally, two weeks after the attack, Guilford Budd was recovering but was “badly disfigured for life.”³³ With this, we must realize that during the political affairs and all of the publicly reported misfortunes and mishaps Guilford endured, Budd was not only illiterate but was also badly maimed.

In the light of these facts, and given the many instances of public humiliation he endured, we must conclude that Guilford Budd was a man who had a tremendous sense of self and self-worth. Although he was a former slave, he was a man of pride and he, quite obviously, never hid from public sight and never shirked being in the public eye. Where others probably would have curled up and died, Guilford did not and continued to exercise his freedom and stamped his presence on early Pueblo history. Although he and his wife were illiterate, he “made his mark” on several legal documents

³¹ Colorado Weekly Chieftain. October 5, 1871. Pueblo, CO.

³² “Fiendish Atrocity.” Colorado Weekly Chieftain. July 27, 1871. Pueblo, CO.

³³ Colorado Weekly Chieftain. August 10, 1871. Pueblo, CO.

including property ownership, and that mark, although just a simple X, was his mark – and his lone - and it is not difficult to imagine that he made that mark proudly and in full defiance of anyone who opposed him.

Finally, Guilford Budd began to exhibit some mental and physical deterioration around 1886 and was committed to the State Insane Asylum on January 3, 1887.³⁴ He passed away almost two months later of paralysis and was buried on the grounds with no mention of public or private fanfare or pomp.³⁵

But the story of Guilford Budd does not end here...

The remainder of his story centered around a piece of property located in Third Street. I must stress that the property was, quite literally, IN Third Street. Curiously, there is no mention of the property being formally purchased in the Pueblo County property registers and no tax was assessed against the property in Pueblo County from 1874 to 1890³⁶, but, as early as 1876, mention was made that Budd had an adobe and frame building that sat in Third Street facing Santa Fe Avenue from the east. This building was converted to a kind of second-hand store in 1876 where sewing machines and guns and other kinds of goods could be had.³⁷ Also, this was the last piece of real estate owned by Guilford's widow, Annie Budd. The other properties had been sold with the settlement of Guilford's estate.³⁸

Previously, in 1885, the adobe and frame building in Third Street collapsed and Guilford appealed to the City of Pueblo to be allowed to rebuild the structure using the materials at hand (they were still present at the site), whereupon the City refused.³⁹ Shortly after Guilford's death, the city

³⁴ "Guilford Budd - Patient 455." January 4, 1887. Patient General Register. Colorado State Insane Asylum. Colorado Mental Health Institute Museum. Pueblo, CO.

³⁵ Ibid. and "Guilford Courthouse Budd." Colorado Daily Chieftain. February 25, 1887.

³⁶ Robinson, T.M. "Pueblo vs. Budd." Cases Adjudged in the Supreme Court of Colorado. Banks & Brothers Law Publishers, 1894. New York and Albany.

³⁷ Colorado Daily Chieftain. September 12, 1876. Pueblo, CO.

³⁸ "Property Sale." Colorado Daily Chieftain. August 5, 1888. Pueblo, CO. Lots 12, 13 and 14 of Block 20, Old Pueblo Townsite valued at \$700. Back tax was due in the amount of \$35.35.

³⁹ Colorado Daily Chieftain. October 31, 1885. Pueblo, CO.

decided to continue Third Street east of Santa Fe Avenue and made plans to begin grading. In response, the estate of Guilford Budd formally filed suit against the City of Pueblo in 1889.⁴⁰

In April, the formal suit against the city was made and claimed that Annie Budd was the legal owner of the property which amounted to 22 feet of frontage within Third Street as it faced Santa Fe Avenue.⁴¹ Later that month, both sides prepared for a fight...

On May 4, 1890, the Colorado Daily Chieftain reported that the District Judge had questioned the legality of notices that were served and threw the case out of court. In retaliation, the attorney for Annie built a fence around the property in Third Street.⁴² The City quickly came in and destroyed the fence.

The case was reheard in Trinidad a few weeks later on motion of an “injunction to restrain the City from exercising any acts of ownership.” The case was denied by the judge and the Chieftain proudly claimed “second blood for the City.”⁴³

Interestingly, the “massive one-and-a-quarter page story” mentioned in the April 2022 Lore article was published at this time in the Daily Chieftain on June 1, 1890 – complete with cartoons (one of the first of its kind) – and included descriptions of Budd that were fairly demeaning and insulting. The article went on in quite ironic language to mention his illiteracy, questioned his intelligence and reaffirmed that Budd “was emphatically a self made (sic.) man and he made an uncommonly poor job of himself” – even though he had been dead for over four years. We must wonder why the Chieftain would take the time to insult and defame a dead man when legal proceedings were taking place against his widow – who was not mentioned in the article.

Anyway, by December of 1890, the fence had been rebuilt around the property and the case

⁴⁰ Colorado Daily Chieftain. November 19, 1889. Pueblo, CO.

⁴¹ Colorado Daily Chieftain. April 9, 1890. Pueblo, CO.

⁴² Colorado Daily Chieftain. May 9, 1890. Pueblo, CO.

⁴³ Colorado Daily Chieftain. May 20, 1890. Pueblo, CO.

heard again in the district court. This time, the suit was found in favor of Annie Budd – and the City quickly filed an appeal to the Supreme Court of Colorado.⁴⁴ The matter was declared in abeyance as the case was officially entered into the Supreme Court in January.⁴⁵

Shortly afterward, another insult was lobbed against the deceased Guilford Budd by the Chieftain on June 22, 1891 when his physical appearance (and intelligence) was compared to that of the noted French photographer Hippolyte Bayard who had “the genuine Missouri cornfield cut” about him.⁴⁶

Finally, in late February 1894, the Colorado Supreme Court deliberated on the case and motion was found in favor of Annie Budd on April 18, 1894. The grounds for the decision were cited upon the fact the Guilford and Annie Budd occupied the property in question since 1867 - before Pueblo was officially organized as a townsite on January 19, 1869. Therefore, the Court found that the City had no valid title owned or even related to the property and went on to decide that Pueblo’s first probate judge, Mark Bradford, had no right to include the private property as part of a public thoroughfare in the first Plat of Pueblo Townsite, or “the Fosdick Plat” later in 1869. Additionally, the Supreme Court found that Third Street east of Santa Fe Avenue was blocked by the foot of Tenderfoot Hill (now under I-25 and the Sangre de Cristo Art Center) and expressed no viable interest in the property until 1889; therefore, the City had no right to claim ownership regardless of the Fosdick Plat because it did not have a vested interest in the property at the time.

The Supreme Court added that the Fosdick Plat, created by the decision of Judge Mark Bradford that ignored properties owned by private individuals was “in conflict with proper execution of his trust” and “the act of the probate judge...was void.”⁴⁷

⁴⁴ Colorado Daily Chieftain. December 2, 1890. Pueblo, CO.

⁴⁵ Colorado Daily Chieftain. January 23, 1891. Pueblo, CO.

⁴⁶ “Hippolyte’s Pictures.” Colorado Daily Chieftain. June 22, 1891. Pueblo, CO.

⁴⁷ Robinson, T.M. “Pueblo vs. Budd.” Cases Adjudged in the Supreme Court of Colorado. Banks & Brothers Law Publishers, 1894. New York and Albany.

The value of the 22-foot piece of Third Street was estimated at about \$15,000⁴⁸ and was purchased by the City from Annie Budd for \$5000 in 1899.⁴⁹

By this time, Annie Budd (or Budds – she seemed to prefer this version of the name) lived in Colorado Springs.⁵⁰ She passed away on August 2, 1904 and is interred in an unmarked grave in Greenwood Cemetery. There was no public mention of her death.

It should be mentioned that Annie Budd's life is as interesting as her husband's – but even less information is available about her. Socially, there were several strikes against Guilford and Annie Budd at the time. They were both African American former slaves during the period of post-Civil War Reconstruction. Already, their social positions should be considered very tenuous; but in direct contradiction to what was socially expected of African Americans at the time, they both exhibited some social ambitions and did score some success.

They were also both illiterate – and consequently, this, and given their race, made them quite obvious easy and easily accessible targets in a community that was constantly changing as the American West was opened to further settlement. It should also be mentioned that Annie had one additional strike against her – she was a woman in a male dominated society and had to face unique problems while her husband was alive – which only worsened after his death.

As difficult as it may be to admit, through the story of Guilford Budd, it becomes clear that early Pueblo did not escape the post-Civil War social disruptions of the time and was as susceptible to a strange kind of instinct to marginalize those who were easily marginalized. It was not some kind of ever-receptive utopia nestled along the banks of the Arkansas River.

However, in a small place like Pueblo in the late 1860s, even though Guilford suffered many humiliations here, he would have reminded us that because of his courage, he was able to be as free as

⁴⁸ Colorado Daily Chieftain. April 18, 1894. Pueblo, CO.

⁴⁹ "For Health Fund." Colorado Daily Chieftain. February 7, 1899. Pueblo, CO.

⁵⁰ Colorado Springs, Colorado City Directory, 1903. Colorado Springs, CO.

he wanted to be in his new-found home along the Arkansas.

It is possible to see Guilford's life as exceptional and heroic given the political aspirations attributed to him – if the whole story is not sorted out. It is also just as easy to see his life as tragic and touched by cruelty and racism – but then, just as now, it is easy to turn the life of Guilford Budd into some kind of fable or passion play or parable for social justice – just as it was in 1890 and 2022. Either heroic or tragic, at the heart of it, Guilford was simply an exceptional man who lived according to his own terms during a time he could be as free as he wanted. Guilford Budd was a man who was an easy target because of the color of his skin, his proud personality and his public fearlessness, but it was this uniqueness that also caused him to be singled out publicly – and consequently, 150 years later, we know more about him than we do about others who were more 'mainstream.'

Guilford, however, would simply assert that he was a man – and he would emphasize that he was a free man – and he would add that he lived his life on his own terms. He would also remind us that he did more in his unconventional life than some could ever hope for – and he did all of this courageously, with a sense of good will, a sense of humor and a sense of self that none of his worst detractors could ever take away and he would never bear the humiliation they could ever hope to force upon him. He would also have reminded us that slavery was worse than anything anyone could throw at him...

It is easy for us, in this age of racial sensitivity and political correctness to see the lives of Guilford and Annie Budd as tragic and unfortunate. Regardless, I highly doubt that Guilford would agree with the conclusion that his life was tragic – and it all took place here, along the banks of the Arkansas...

